

Supplemental Table 4 (S4)

Specificity (%) of ME, 18S and 24S α amplicons for identity with registered sequences (GenBank) of *T. cruzi* gene fragments from mammal reservoir taxa. [confidence interval > 95%, CI]. Bonferroni adjusted significance for χ^2 frequencies in bold: lower than expected $^{\dagger\dagger} = p < 0.001$.

	ME specificity % (N) [CI]	18S specificity % (N) [CI]	24S α specificity % (N) [CI]
Primates	81.8^{††} (11) [59.0 - 100.0]	62.5 (8) [29.0 - 96.0]	66.7 (9) [35.9 - 97.5]
Chiroptera	100.0 (55)	64.6 (65) [53.0 - 76.2]	80.0 (20) [62.5 - 97.5]
Didelphimorphia	100.0 (8)	0.0 (1)	66.7 (3) [13.3 - 100.0]
Rodentia	97.1 (35) [91.6 - 100.0]	33.3 (9) [2.5 - 64.1]	52.2 (23) [31.9 - 72.5]
Carnivora (wildlife)	100.0 (2)	100.0 (1)	-
Carnivora (companion)	100.0 (10)	50.0 (2) [0.0 - 100.0]	71.4 (7) [38.0 - 100.0]
Artiodactyla	100.0 (12)	100.0 (1)	100.0 (12)
Perissodactyla	-	-	100.0 (1)
All mammals	97.7 (133) [95.2 - 100.0]	60.9 (87) [50.7 - 71.2]	72.0 (75) [61.8 - 82.2]